

DURABILITY STUDY OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYURETHANE PULTRUDED PLATES SUBJECTED TO WATER IMMERSION

Guijun Xian^{1,2}, Bin Hong^{1,2}, Hui Li^{1,2} and Lili Sui³

¹ Key Lab of Structural Dynamic Behavior and Control (Harbin Institute of Technology)
Ministry of Education, Harbin 150090, China
Email: gjxian@hit.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.hit.edu.cn>

² School of Civil Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150090, China
Email: ahqyhb2008@126.com, web page: <http://www.hit.edu.cn>

³Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Durability for Marine Civil Engineering
Shenzhen University, Shenzhen 518060, China
Email: suill8969@163.com, web page: <http://www.szu.edu.cn>

Keywords: Polyurethane, CFRP plates, Water absorption, Tensile properties, Durability

ABSTRACT

Water absorption and thermal-mechanical properties of polyurethane (PU) resin and pultruded carbon fiber reinforced PU plates (CFPUs) were studied through immersion of specimens in distilled water at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C, respectively. The water uptake of PU resin reached the water saturation about 2.43%, higher than that of an epoxy resin matrix for carbon fiber reinforced composites. PU possessed excellent tensile properties with a high elongation at break (~ 7%). Water immersion at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C for 3 months reduced the tensile strength of PU resin by 29.2%, 20.1% and 11.8%, respectively. The less degradation at higher immersion temperature was attributed to the increased postcuring, which was supported by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) results. The saturation of the water uptake of the pultruded CFPU was realized in 1 month. In addition, after 1 month of immersion in water, the tensile strength of CFPU was not degraded. This indicates that the current CFPU shows super water resistance compared to the epoxy based plates.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is known that the resin matrices of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are usually epoxy resin, vinyl resin and polyester. Polyurethane resins with excellent toughness [1] are usually used as a coating [2, 3], foams [4], shape-memory polymer [5, 6] and nanocomposites [7] in previous papers. In recent years, polyurethane resins are increasingly being used in FRP composites [8-13], but most of them [8-11] are glass fiber reinforced polyurethane (GFPU) composites. In other words, carbon fiber reinforced PU (CFPU) composites have not been studied deeply. In addition, FRP composites are used in marine, offshore and civil infrastructure applications in this study. FRP composites are affected inevitably by moisture and even water immersion at elevated temperature. Thus, it is urgent to study the effects of hygrothermal ageing on CFPU composites.

The effects of hygrothermal ageing on PU resin were studied by few authors [14, 15]. Davies and Evrard [14] reported that the life of tensile strength (50% property loss) for PU resin immersed in artificial sea water at sea temperatures was in excess of 100 years according to a linear Arrhenius extrapolation. As mentioned by Davies and Evrard [14], the resin formulations are multiplicity. Therefore, it is necessary to study the hygrothermal ageing of each kind of PU resin used.

There are few papers reporting the effects of hygrothermal ageing on fiber reinforced PU (FPU) composites. Mourad, et al. [16] has indicated effects of seawater and temperature on the structural properties of glass/epoxy and glass/polyurethane composite materials. In this report, no significant changes were observed in tensile strength of glass/epoxy and in modulus of both glass/epoxy and glass/polyurethane composites. However, the tensile strength of the glass/polyurethane composites

decreased by 19% after 1 year of exposure to seawater at room temperature and by 31% after 1 year of exposure at 65 °C. It has been revealed that moisture affected the properties of both glass/epoxy and glass/polyurethane composites by dual mechanism of stress-relaxation-swelling-mechanical adhesion, and breakdown of chemical bonds between fiber and matrix at the interface. However, there are still no papers found to report the effects of hygrothermal ageing on CFPU composites. Thus, it is an urgent thing to study the degradation law and its mechanism of relevant properties of CFPU composites subjected to hygrothermal ageing.

As a new resin applied into FRP composites, PU resin immersed in distilled water at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C was studied to investigate the degradation law and its mechanism of water absorption and tensile properties. In order to further explore the feasibility of PU resin used in FRP composites, the water absorption and tensile properties of CFPU also immersed in distilled water at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C were studied as well as the interfacial properties between carbon fibers and PU resins by in-plane shear strength (IPSS). In addition, the relevant properties of epoxy resin and epoxy/CFRP plates were compared with the corresponding properties of PU resin and epoxy/CFRP plates to assess the relevant properties of PU resin and epoxy/CFRP plates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Raw materials

Two components polyurethane (Elastocoat C6226/101) produced by BASF Polyurethane Specialties (China) was used in this study. The ratio of polyol component and isocyanate component is 1:1.259. Polyols component was dehydrated in a vacuum oven at 110 °C for 4 hours. PU plates were cured in an oven at 200 °C for 15 minutes. The epoxy resin mentioned in this study is oligomeric prepolymer diglycidyl ether bisphenol-A epoxy resin, and its hardener is methyl hexahydro-phthalic anhydride (MeHHPA).

The CFPU and epoxy/CFRP plates with 25 mm × 1.46 mm of section size were both prepared with the pultrusion machine at the laboratory for FRP composites and structures (Harbin Institute of Technology, China). The carbon fiber for CFPU is produced by Sinopec (Shanghai, China) and its tensile strength is close to that of T700 carbon fiber. It is noted that the carbon fiber of epoxy/CFRP plates mentioned in this study is Tairyfil carbon fiber (TC-36S, 12K).

2.2 Water immersion

Distilled water was used as the immersion environments at 23 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C. All specimens were dried at 60 °C in an oven for 2 days before water immersion. It is worth noting that 60 °C is lower than the glass transition temperature of PU resin and CFPU to not change the resin molecular structures.

Specimens for water absorption were cut into 25 mm × 25 mm × 2 mm for PU resin, and 25 mm × 25 mm × 1.46 mm for CFPU, respectively. It is noted that the sizes of epoxy resin and epoxy/CFRP plates mentioned are 25 mm × 25 mm × 3.8 mm and 25 mm × 25 mm × 1.46 mm, respectively. The weight gain (%) was detected by periodically recording the mass of the samples according to Ref. [17]. Specimens were taken out of the baths, swiped off the surface water using tissue paper, and then weighed with an electronic balance with an accuracy of 0.01 mg. The presented data are an average of 15 coupons for each condition. The weight gain at time t (M_t) of the sample is defined as

$$M_t = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where W_t is the wet weight, W_0 is the initial weight after drying at 60 °C for two days.

2.3 Tensile properties

The Tensile properties of the resin samples with 115 mm of length, 6 mm of width of narrow section and 2 mm of thickness were tested according to ASTM D 638-2010 (Standard Test Methods for Tensile Properties of Plastics). The tensile properties of CFRP samples with size of 250 mm × 25

mm × 1.46 mm were tested according to ASTM D 3039-2010 (Standard Test Methods for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials). Speed of testing of the two specimens is 5 mm/min. For each condition, five samples were repeated and the average results were reported.

2.4 In-plane shear strength (IPSS)

In-plane shear strength (IPSS) is defined as the strength making the FRP composites stratified from the cross section (Seeing in Fig. 1) in this study. The size of specimens for IPSS tests is 25 mm × 10 mm × 1.46 mm. To make sure the stability of IPSS, specimens were stratified at the middle position in the width direction (Seeing in Fig. 1). For each condition, five samples were repeated and the average results were reported. Speed of testing is 1 mm/min. The IPSS can be calculated by the following equation

$$IPSS = \frac{P}{hb} \quad (1)$$

where P is the load, h is the thickness of specimens, and b is the width of specimens.

Figure 1: The schematics of IPSS test.

2.5 DMTA tests

DMTA (Q800, TA) was conducted on specimens of 40 mm × 8 mm × 2 mm for PU resin and 35 mm × 10 mm × 1.46 mm for CFPU, respectively. The DMTA tests for PU resin were performed with tensile film mode, 1 Hz frequency heating from 25 °C and 200 °C at 5 °C/min. The DMTA tests for CFPU were performed with a single cantilever mode, 1 Hz frequency heating from 25 °C and 200 °C at 5 °C/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water absorption of resin

According to the results obtained by this water absorption test, the weight gain of PU resin and epoxy resin shows remarkable differences. After immersed in distilled water for 3 months, PU resin has reached the water saturation while water uptake of epoxy resin has still increased at different rates in the three immersion environments.

The water uptake curves of PU resin were observed to follow the classic Fick's law [18]. For 1-D moisture absorption, on both sides of the sample to the same environment, the weight gain, M_t , can be described as

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2} \exp\left[-\frac{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 Dt}{h^2}\right] \quad (2)$$

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{kh}{4M_\infty} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

where M_∞ is the level of quasi-equilibrium water uptake, h is the thickness of the specimen (equal to 2 mm, 3.8 mm, 1.46 mm for PU resin, epoxy resin, and CFRP plates, respectively), t is the immersion time, and n is the summation index. D is the diffusion coefficient of water molecules has the form of Eq. (3), where k is the initial slope of the plot of M_t versus $t^{1/2}$. M_∞ of PU resin was determined to be equal to 2.43%. D calculated according to Eq. (3), as well as other parameters, was listed in Table 1. It is noted that M_{max} listed in Table 1 is the weight gain of specimens after 3 months of immersion. As can be seen in Table 1, M_{max} at both 20 °C and 40 °C of water immersion is a little higher than M_{max} at 60 °C of immersion. This may be caused by the degradation at 60 °C of immersion or the postcuring of PU resin leading to the formation of crosslink network structure. The later reason was proved by the following DMTA analysis. D increased with immersion temperature. It is known that D at 60 °C of immersion made the biggest value which is almost 12 times than D at 20 °C of immersion.

The relationship between diffusion coefficient D and temperature T is described by the following Arrhenius equation

$$D = D_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

The activation energy E_a was obtained by plotting $\ln D$ versus $1/T$ according to Arrhenius rate equation, given by

$$\ln(D) = \ln(D_0) - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (5)$$

where R is the universal gas constant (equal to $8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), D_0 is the diffusion constant. According to Eq. (5), E_a for PU resin immersed in distilled water was determined to be 50.20 KJ/mol.

Temperature (°C)	PU resin			Epoxy resin			
	M_∞ (%)	M_{max} (%)	D ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$)	M_∞ (%)	M_{3m} (%)	M_{max} (%)	D ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$)
20	2.43	2.48	2.31	0.35	0.39	0.43	6.26
40	2.43	2.47	7.96	0.42	0.50	0.56	24.17
60	2.43	2.43	27.44	0.53	0.69	0.77	61.14

Table 1: Water absorption and diffusion parameters for PU and epoxy immersed in distilled water.

As mentioned earlier, PU resin shows good water uptake properties. However, the water uptake of PU resin is a little higher than that of epoxy resin. Water uptake curves of epoxy resin ($h = 3.8 \text{ mm}$) immersed in distilled water for 6 months were observed to follow the two-stage model [21] other than Fick's law. According to the two-stage model, quasi-equilibrium water uptake was determined to be 0.35%, 0.42% and 0.53% at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C of immersion, respectively. D of epoxy resin was also calculated by Eq. (3). Diffusion parameters of epoxy resin were listed in Table 1. It is noted that M_{3m} is the weight gain of epoxy resin immersed in distilled water for 3 months. According to Eq. (5), E_a of epoxy resin in water immersion is equal to 46.39 KJ/mol. These results indicated that epoxy resin shown quite low water uptake. It is noted that D of epoxy resin was significantly higher than that of PU resin. This result was caused by the nearly twice thickness of epoxy specimens than that of PU specimens. Therefore, the activation energy of epoxy resin is close to that of PU resin.

Although a significantly low water uptake epoxy resin shown, water uptake of PU resin immersed in distilled water for 3 months has reached water saturation while water uptake of epoxy resin has still increased at 6 months of water immersion. In addition, the relatively little higher activation energy of PU resin than that of epoxy resin indicated that PU resin immersed in distilled water possessed relatively lower activity. However, PU resin shows relatively poor water absorption and diffusion properties. It is believed that this does not affect the application of PU resin into FRP composites.

3.2 Tensile properties of resin

Tensile properties of PU resin immersed in distilled water for 3 months were investigated to study the degradation law and its mechanism. Due to the excellent toughness of PU resin, the curve of tensile stress-strain has obvious yield stage (Seeing in Fig. 2). Compared with PU resin, epoxy resin has no yield stage (Seeing in Fig. 2). The tensile yield strength, tensile modulus, and elongation at break of PU resin are 83.16 ± 0.08 MPa, 2.88 ± 0.04 GPa and $6.95 \pm 0.70\%$, respectively. However, epoxy resin has 76.13 ± 0.46 MPa of break strength, 2.91 ± 0.13 GPa of tensile modulus and $3.20 \pm 0.19\%$ of elongation at break. The tensile properties of PU resin are slightly higher than that of epoxy resin.

Figure 2: Tensile stress-strain curves of control PU samples, PU samples immersed in water for three months, and control epoxy sample.

After 3 months of immersion, the tensile properties of PU resin decreased at various degrees (Seeing in Table 2). It is noted that tensile yield strength reduced 29.2%, 20.1% and 11.8% at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C of water immersion, respectively. Tensile modulus decreased slightly with immersion temperature. Elongation at yield, lower than the initial value at all temperatures of immersion, increased with immersion temperature. Elongation at break has shown the similar law as elongation at yield except from specimens at 20 °C of immersion. It is noted that the significantly increasing of elongation at break at 20 °C of immersion indicated specimens at 20 °C of immersion has not been postcured but plasticized. However, the reductions of tensile properties of PU specimens may be caused by plasticization while the increasing of tensile properties with immersion temperature was attributed to the formation of a secondary crosslink network which was explained in DMTA analysis mentioned later.

Environments	Yield Strength (MPa)	Break Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Elongation at Yield (%)	Elongation at Break (%)
Pristine of Epoxy	No Yield	76.13 ± 0.46	2.91 ± 0.13	No Yield	3.20 ± 0.19
Pristine of PU	83.16 ± 0.08	80.24 ± 1.67	2.88 ± 0.04	5.33 ± 0.10	6.95 ± 0.70
20 °C Water	58.90 ± 0.46	51.56 ± 1.09	2.70 ± 0.07	3.80 ± 0.07	11.87 ± 1.74
40 °C Water	66.42 ± 0.67	62.76 ± 0.84	2.67 ± 0.04	4.23 ± 0.11	6.15 ± 0.75
60 °C Water	73.34 ± 0.23	71.43 ± 1.28	2.54 ± 0.04	5.05 ± 0.15	6.72 ± 0.17

Table 2: Tensile properties of PU samples immersed in distilled water for 3 months, and epoxy sample controlled.

As mentioned above, PU resin has excellent tensile properties than that of epoxy resin. However, the most important advantage of PU resin is the excellent toughness reflected in the tensile stress-strain curves (Seeing in Fig. 2). In addition, the durability for tensile properties of PU resin immersed in distilled water for 3 months has not shown irreversible degradation. Therefore, PU resin can be applied into FRP composites.

3.3 DMTA tests of resin

DMTA tests were performed to assess the effects of hygrothermal ageing on the viscoelastic response of PU resin immersed in distilled water for 2 months. For these purposes, the effects on glass transition temperature (T_g) and the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) curve were emphasized. The initial values of T_g of PU resin was 111.20 °C by $\tan \delta$.

As shown in Fig. 3, the loss tangent curves have shown two obvious peaks. The lower height peak remained the same abscissa as the initial loss tangent curves while the higher height peak shifted to the left, which was due to plasticization resulting in disturbance of interchain bonding in PU resin. It is easy to be seen that T_g decreased after 2 months of water immersion, which was believed to be caused by the plasticization and water uptake. However, T_g at 60 °C of water immersion increased a little. This result followed the earlier results of Zhou and Lucas [22] who hypothesized that T_g initially decrease till the bulk polymer is saturated after which it increases again. Zhou and Lucas [22] reported that Type II bound water increasing with exposure temperature and time formed a secondary crosslink network resulting an increase in T_g in water saturated epoxy resin. Combing with the results of water absorption mentioned earlier, PU specimens ($h = 2$ mm) have already reached water saturation after 2 months of immersion. Thus, Type II bound water defined by Zhou and Lucas [22] increased to lead to the increase in T_g . It is believed that this is why the tensile properties of PU resin increased with immersion temperature after 3 months of water immersion. In addition, the loss tangent height and the width of the peak decreased with immersion temperature after 2 months of immersion. Furthermore, the width of the peak comparing with the initial width of the peak increased. These results clearly indicated the effects of water uptake and immersion temperature on viscoelastic response.

Figure 3: Tangent delta curves of PU samples immersed in water for 2 months.

3.4 Water absorption of CFRP plates

The water absorption and diffusion of CFPU in water immersion was also investigated to evaluate the water resistance. According to the results of experiments in this study, the water uptake curves of CFPU were considered to follow Fick's law, which was consisted with the water absorption law of PU resin. It is noted that CFPU for water absorption tests were immersed in distilled water for only 1 month. Due to CFPU specimens in water immersion at 60 °C were close to water saturation and according to Fick's law, the quasi-equilibrium water uptake can be calculated by fitting the curve of water immersion at 60 °C with the following equation

$$M_t = M_\infty \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{Dt}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \right\} \quad (6)$$

Thus, M_∞ of CFPU specimens at 60 °C of immersion was determined to be 0.64%. Considering M_∞ at all temperatures of immersion for PU resin possessed the same value, M_∞ at 20°C and 40 °C of immersion for CFPU specimens was also determined to be 0.64%. Using the same processing method as PU resin, diffusion parameters were listed in Table 3. These results have shown that CFPU

possessed quite low water absorption. In addition, E_a of CFPU for water immersion was determined to be 45.81 KJ/mol.

Temperature (°C)	CFPUs			Epoxy/CFRP plates			
	M_∞ (%)	M_{max} (%)	D ($\times 10^{-7}$ mm ² /s)	M_∞ (%)	M_{Im} (%)	M_{max} (%)	D ($\times 10^{-7}$ mm ² /s)
20	0.64	0.30	0.41	0.51	0.22	0.61	0.24
40	0.64	0.47	1.13	0.84	0.49	0.90	0.41
60	0.64	0.63	3.93	1.25	0.82	1.41	0.82

Table 3: Water absorption and diffusion parameters for CFPUs and epoxy based CFRPs.

The water uptake curves of epoxy/CFRP plates immersed in distilled water for 15 months were also observed to follow the two-stage model. Diffusion parameters were calculated and listed in Table 3. Compared with diffusion properties for CFPUs immersed in distilled water, epoxy/CFRP plates have relatively higher water uptake although the diffusion coefficients of epoxy/CFRP plates were lower than those of CFPUs. It is noted that M_{Im} , higher than M_{max} of CFPU specimens, is the water uptake of epoxy/CFRP specimens at 1 month of immersion. E_a of epoxy/CFRP for water immersion was determined to be 24.86 KJ/mol. The lower activation energy of epoxy/CFRP indicated that epoxy/CFRP specimens were more active in water immersion. However, CFPU has shown better diffusivity in water immersion.

3.5 Tensile properties of CFRP plates

Tensile properties of CFPUs immersed in distilled water for 1 month were investigated to study the durability in water immersion. CFPUs made by the laboratory of FRP composites and structures in Harbin Institute of Technology have 2.18 ± 0.08 GPa of tensile strength, 172.23 ± 7.69 GPa of tensile modulus and $1.28 \pm 0.07\%$ of elongation at break.

Figure 4: Tensile strength for CFPUs (a) and epoxy based CFRP plates (b) as a function of immersion time at various temperatures.

Since tensile modulus and elongation at break changed little, tensile strength of CFPUs immersed in distilled water for 14 days and 30 days was alone shown in Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 4, tensile strength decreased with immersion time and immersion temperature. To evaluate the durability of tensile properties of CFPUs immersed in distilled water, tensile strength of epoxy/CFRP plates immersed in distilled water were also shown in Fig. 4. Tensile strength, tensile modulus and elongation at break of epoxy/CFRP made by the same laboratory with CFPUs were 2.48 GPa, 172.78 GPa and 1.42%, respectively. As can be seen in shown Fig. 4, tensile strength of CFPUs remained

better residual strength after 1 month of water immersion. This result indicated that CFPUs have more superior durability in water immersion. However, the better durability in water immersion will promote the application of CFPUs into civil engineering.

3.6 IPSS

To investigate the interfacial strength between carbon fibers and resins, in-plane shear strength (IPSS) of CFPUs immersed in distilled water for 1 month was tested. As shown in Fig. 5, IPSS of specimens decreased with immersion time and immersion temperature. It is noted that the higher value of IPSS of specimens at 60 °C of immersion than that of specimens at 40 °C of immersion for 14 days may be caused by plasticization leading to the increasing of interfacial strength. After 1 month of immersion, IPSS of specimens remained 88.30%, 88.09% and 83.58% of residual strength at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C of water immersion, respectively. It is believed that the reduction of IPSS affected the tensile properties of CFPUs.

Figure 5: In-plane shear strength of CFPUs.

3.7 DMTA tests of CFRP plates

To investigate the effects of hygrothermal ageing on the viscoelastic response of CFPUs immersed in distilled water for 1 month, glass transition temperature (T_g) and the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) were analyzed. The initial value of T_g of CFPUs was 135.50 °C by $\tan \delta$.

Figure 6: T_g (a) and $\tan \delta$ height (b) as a function of immersion time for CFPUs.

During 1 months of water immersion, T_g decreased with immersion time and immersion temperature (Seeing in Fig. 6a and Fig. 7). It is noted that T_g at 20 °C of immersion did not change. The reductions of T_g were believed to be caused by plasticization of PU resin. It is noted that T_g at higher temperatures of immersion tended to a balance, especially for specimens at 60 °C of immersion.

This result was attributed to the formation of Type II bound water defined by Zhou and Lucas [22]. However, the changes of T_g have explained the degradation of tensile properties of CFPU at a degree. As shown in Fig. 6b, the loss tangent height decreased slightly with immersion temperature and immersion time, which was caused by the plasticization of PU resin. It is noted that the sudden increase in T_g at 40 °C after 1 month of immersion may be caused by the individual differences of specimens. As can be seen in Fig. 7, the shape of the loss tangent changed little, which has shown relative good viscoelastic response.

Figure 7: Tangent delta curves of CFPU immersed in distilled water for 14 days (a) and 31 days (b) at different temperatures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The water uptake of PU resin reached the water saturation about 2.43%, higher than that of an epoxy resin matrix for carbon fiber reinforced composites. PU possessed excellent tensile properties with a high elongation at break (~ 7%). Water immersion at 20°C, 40°C and 60°C for 3 months reduced the tensile strength of PU resin by 29.2%, 20.1% and 11.8%, respectively. The less degradation at higher immersion temperature was attributed to the increased postcuring, which was supported by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) results. The saturation of the water uptake of the pultruded CFPU was realized in 1 month. In addition, after 1 month of immersion in water, the tensile strength of CFPU was not degraded. This indicates that the current CFPU shows super water resistance compared to the epoxy based plates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for the financial support from the NSFC with Grant No. 51178147 and 51178271, the National Key Basic Research Program of China (973 Program) with Grant No. 2012CB026200, the Key Fundamental Research Project of Shenzhen Science & Technology Research Fund (JC201005250051A).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Han, et al., *CNT buckypaper/thermoplastic polyurethane composites with enhanced stiffness, strength and toughness*, Composites Science and Technology, 103, 2014, pp. 63-71.
- [2] T.T.X. Hang, et al., *Effect of silane modified nano ZnO on UV degradation of polyurethane coatings*, Progress in Organic Coatings, 79, 2015, pp. 68-74.
- [3] G. Wang, et al., *Synthesis of HDI/IPDI hybrid isocyanurate and its application in polyurethane coating*, Progress in Organic Coatings, 78, 2015, pp. 225-233.

- [4] Y. Savelyev, et al., *Preparation and characterization of new biologically active polyurethane foams*, Materials Science and Engineering: C, 45, 2014, pp. 127-135.
- [5] B. Weidenfeller and M. Anhalt, *Polyurethane-magnetite composite shape-memory polymer: Thermal properties*, Journal of Thermoplastic Composite materials, 27(7), 2014, pp. 895-908.
- [6] D. Santiago, F. Ferrando and S. De la Flor, *Effect of different shape-memory processing methods on the thermomechanical cyclic properties of a shape-memory polyurethane*, Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance, 37(7), 2014, pp. 2561-2566.
- [7] P. Pokharel and D.S. Lee, *High performance polyurethane nanocomposite films prepared from a masterbatch of graphene oxide in polyether polyol*, Chemical Engineering Journal, 253, 2014, pp. 356-365.
- [8] H.S. Da Costa Mattos, et al., *Analysis of a glass fibre reinforced polyurethane composite repair system for corroded pipelines at elevated temperatures*, Composite Structures, 114, 2014, pp. 117-123.
- [9] H. Luo, et al., *Characterization of the compressive behavior of glass fiber reinforced polyurethane foam at different strain rates*, Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering-Transactions of the ASME, 132(0213012), 2010.
- [10] B. Suresha, *Friction and dry slide wear of short glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic polyurethane composites*, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 29(7), 2010, pp. 1055-1061.
- [11] J.M.L. Reis, F.L. Chaves and H.S. Da Costa Mattos, *Tensile behaviour of glass fibre reinforced polyurethane at different strain rates*, Materials & Design, 49, 2013, pp. 192-196.
- [12] Z.B. Haber, K.R. Mackie and L. Zhao, *Mechanical and environmental loading of concrete beams strengthened with epoxy and polyurethane matrix carbon fiber laminates*, Construction and Building Materials, 26(1), 2012, pp. 604-612.
- [13] S. Jiang, et al., *Effect of surface silanization of carbon fiber on mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced polyurethane composites*, Composites Science and Technology, 110, 2015, pp. 87-94.
- [14] P. Davies, and G. Evrard, *Accelerated ageing of polyurethanes for marine applications*, Polymer Degradation and Stability, 92(8), 2007, pp. 1455-1464.
- [15] R.N. Jana, and H. Bhunia, *Accelerated hygrothermal and UV aging of thermoplastic polyurethanes*, High Performance Polymers, 22(1), 2010, pp. 3-15.
- [16] A.I. Mourad, et al., *Effect of seawater and warm environment on glass/epoxy and glass/polyurethane composites*, Applied Composite Materials, 17(5), 2010, pp. 557-573.
- [17] M. Wrosch, G.J. Xian, and V.M. Karbhari, *Moisture absorption and desorption in a UV cured urethane acrylate adhesive based on radiation source*, Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 107(6), 2008, pp. 3654-3662.
- [18] J.P. Pascault, et al., *Thermosetting polymers*. Vol. 64, 2002: CRC Press.
- [19] J.W. Chin, T. Nguyen, and K. Aouadi, *Sorption and diffusion of water, salt water, and concrete pore solution in composite matrices*, Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 71(3), 1999, pp. 483-492.
- [20] J. Crank, *The mathematics of diffusion*. 1979: Oxford university press.
- [21] V.M. Karbhari, and G.J. Xian, *Hygrothermal effects on high V_F pultruded unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites: Moisture uptake*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 40(1), 2009, pp. 41-49.
- [22] J. M. Zhou, J. P. Lucas. *Hygrothermal effects of epoxy resin. Part II: variations of glass transition temperature*, Polymer, 40(20), 1999, pp. 5513-5522.